

Computational Estimation of the Hemodynamic Significance of Coronary Stenoses in Arterial Branches deriving from CCTA: a proof-of-concept study

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Abstract—The development of non-invasive methods for the accurate hemodynamic assessment of the coronary vasculature has become a non-trivial matter for the everyday clinical practice. Virtual Functional Assessment Index has already been suggested as a valid alternative to the invasively measured FFR but only on coronary arterial segments. In this work, we propose a novel method for the estimation of the severity of coronary lesions in arterial branches from CCTA derived images. Four left arterial branches were reconstructed in 3D using our in-house developed 3D reconstruction algorithm, and were subjected to computational blood flow simulations for the final calculation of the vFAI through the whole arterial branch. Strong correlation was found ($r=0.82$) between the two methods. A small relative error of 3.2% and a small trend of overestimation (0.023, $SD=0.088$) were also observed. All pathological cases presenting ischemia, were correctly discriminated by our method as hemodynamically significant lesions.

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of non-invasive techniques that can reliably assess the hemodynamic significance of coronary lesions has become of utmost importance in today's clinical practice, since the mortality due to CardioVascular Diseases (CVD) has increased tremendously during the past decades and follows a steadily increasing trend. The most common and efficient non-invasive cardiac imaging modality that has gained substantial ground regarding its use in everyday clinical practice is Coronary Computed Tomography Angiography (CCTA). CCTA has the ability to provide an optical insight of the entire coronary vasculature and can safely assess the severity of any present stenosis, as well as the extent and the type of existing atherosclerotic plaques.

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Numerous 3D reconstruction algorithms utilizing CCTA images have been reported in the literature [1-2].

Fractional Flow Reserve (FFR) is considered as the gold standard for the hemodynamic assessment of coronary stenoses for patients that undergo Interventional Coronary Angiography (ICA). FFR is defined as the ratio of the pressure distal to the examined stenosis to the pressure proximal and it is measured under the induction of hyperemia using an appropriate vasodilator and a dedicated pressure-flow wire. FFR values ≤ 0.80 indicate ischemia and can be safely considered as suitable candidates for Percutaneous Coronary Intervention (PCI).

The application of Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) on the 3D models deriving from CCTA has given the opportunity to calculate important hemodynamic factors such as endothelial pressures and assess the hemodynamic relevance of coronary stenoses. Several attempts have been made and are reported in the literature [3-13]. The main drawback of these methods lies on the fact that a very long computational time is required to complete an assessment of a single patient and in most of the cases, the need of a remote core-laboratory analysis. The development and evaluation of the virtual Functional Assessment Index (vFAI) has already been validated and established as a valid surrogate for the invasively measured FFR [14]. It has been used solely on ICA derived 3D anatomical models and has the ability to assess the hemodynamic significance of coronary stenoses on certain arterial segments.

In this work, we try to increase the efficacy and applicability of the vFAI by expanding its' use on entire arterial branches, and more particularly on sets that include the left coronary vasculature (i.e Left Main artery, Left Arterior Descending artery and Left Circumflex artery). For this purpose, we reconstructed in 3D four arterial branches using our in-house developed algorithm and calculated the respective vFAIs for the entire branch simultaneously. We then compared the calculated vFAIs to the ones calculated using single segments (calculated using the traditional vFAI procedure on arterial segments), as well as to the invasively measured FFR. The scope of this study is to prove and validate the efficacy of the vFAI on arterial branches instead of simple coronary segments, and thus establish a method of non-invasive hemodynamic assessment of the full coronary vasculature, which requires relatively low computational time and does not require the use of a remote core-laboratory analysis, nor the use of a dedicated flow-pressure wire and the induction of hyperemia using intravenous adenosine,

lowering to a minimum the total cost of the assessment and by improving significantly the quality of care for the patient.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Dataset

A group of four patients that underwent CCTA analysis (64-slice General Electric Medical Systems Discovery PET/CT 690® scanner), as well as FFR assessment (ComboWire, Volcano Corp, Rancho Cordova, CA) was included in the current study. The left branch of the coronary vasculature was used in all cases (LM, LAD and LCx). These branches were analyzed because a measured FFR was available for both the LAD and the LCx in all cases.

B. 3D Reconstruction

The 3D reconstruction of the aforementioned four left coronary branches was performed using our in-house developed 3D reconstruction algorithm [15].

Our algorithm is based on an eight-step approach: a) the CCTA images are pre-processed by utilizing the well-known Frangi Vesselness filter [16], a filter that narrows the region of interest (ROI) to regions that most probably belong to coronary vessels. b) The so-called “blooming effect” [17], caused by intensely calcified plaques is subsequently removed. c) By implementing a minimum cost path approach, the 3D centerline of the vessels is then extracted. d) Using a membership function of Hounsfield Units (HU) values and the distance from the centerline, an estimation of the weight function for lumen, outer wall and calcified plaque is made. An extension and fine-tuning of active contour models for e) lumen and f) outer wall segmentation are implemented. The main improvement and enhancement is an additional term forcing the level set to include a prior shape. Regarding the lumen, the prior shape is a tabular mask across centerline with a small radius. g) A level set method is applied regarding the atheromatic plaque segmentation, taking into account calcified objects of significant size. h) Finally, the 3D surfaces for the lumen, outer wall and calcified plaques are created (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: Final 3D model (transparent green: outer wall, brown: lumen) of an LAD-LCx-1st diagonal branch.

Four arterial branches were initially created including the LAD and LCx arteries. For all four cases, the LAD and LCx arteries were also reconstructed separately, resulting to two arteries per patient (Fig.2).

Fig. 2: A) Final 3D reconstructed model of the left coronary branch. B) 3D model of the LAD. C) 3D model of the LCx

C. Blood Flow Simulations

Extending our previously validated vFAI calculation method [20], we applied it on all twelve cases (4 full arterial branches and 8 single artery cases) to examine if the vFAI calculation is feasible in full 3D models of arterial branches. The parameters for the respective blood flow simulations are described below.

a. Rigid Wall Assumption

In order to model blood flow we used the Navier-Stokes and the continuity equations:

$$\rho \frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + \rho(\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v} - \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau} = 0, \quad [1]$$

$$\nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{v}) = 0, \quad [2]$$

where \mathbf{v} is the blood velocity vector and $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ is the stress tensor, which is defined as:

$$\boldsymbol{\tau} = -p\boldsymbol{\delta}_{ij} + 2\mu\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{ij}, \quad [3]$$

where $\boldsymbol{\delta}_{ij}$ is the Kronecker delta, μ is the blood dynamic viscosity, p is the blood pressure and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{ij}$ is the strain tensor calculated as:

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{ij} = \frac{1}{2}(\nabla \mathbf{v} + \nabla \mathbf{v}^T), \quad [4]$$

We applied the properties of a Newtonian fluid regarding blood, with density 1050 kg/m^3 and dynamic viscosity $0.0035 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$. The generated flow was considered laminar and incompressible. The Reynolds number ranged from 565-1733.

b. Boundary Conditions

In order to calculate the vFAI for all twelve cases, we performed two simulations for each model, following the method of Papafaklis et al. [14]. Regarding the inlet, a pressure of 100 mmHg was used in all simulations, a value that corresponds to the average human aortic pressure.

At the outlet, two separate flow rates of 1 and 3 ml/s were applied for each model (i.e. during rest and under stress, respectively). In the single artery simulations, the outlet boundary condition was applied at the distal part of the artery. Regarding the full branch cases, the outlet boundary condition was applied at both arterial ends (Fig.3).

Fig. 3: Boundary conditions for the full branch cases

The pressure gradient was calculated for each case regarding the inlet (P_a) and the outlet (P_d) of the segment examined. Following the aforementioned method [14], we reach the final artery-specific P_d/P_a vs. flow curve:

$$\frac{P_d}{P_a} = 1 - f_v \frac{Q}{P_a} - f_s \frac{Q^2}{P_a}. \quad [5]$$

where Q is the flow rate, f_v is the coefficient of pressure loss due to viscous friction and f_s is the coefficient of pressure loss due to flow separation [18-20]. P_a is then set at 100 mmHg and since the two coefficients were calculated in a previous step, we calculate the area under the P_d/P_a vs. flow curve for a flow that ranges between 0 and 4 ml/s (corresponding to the mean+2SD increase of hyperaemic flow in humans, beginning from a flow of 1 ml/s during rest). The vFAI is then calculated as the ratio of the area under the artery-specific P_d/P_a vs. flow curve to the reference area. Finally, no-slip and no-penetration boundary conditions were used at the arterial wall.

c. Mesh

All twelve 3D models were discretized into tetrahedral elements with an element face size ranging between 0.09 and 0.1 mm and five layers of brick elements were created, beginning from the interface with the arterial wall to the center of the artery, resulting to a total mesh size of around 4.5 million elements. The element size was determined after a mesh sensitivity analysis. The maximum number of iterations for the convergence of the analysis was 50 and the criterion for the convergence was set to 10^{-4} .

III. RESULTS

Our primary goal in this study was to identify the possibility to expand the vFAI framework to full arterial branches and prove that the calculation of the vFAI may be feasible for such cases, thus constituting our method as a non-invasive valid surrogate for the hemodynamic significance of stenoses in coronary arteries. We calculated the vFAI values for each vessel either by applying the method traditionally to each segment or by applying to the full arterial branch, comparing all values to the invasively measured FFR.

TABLE I. CALCULATED vFAIS AND COMPARISON TO ACTUAL FFR

Patient #	Artery	FFR	Branch vFAI	Single Vessel vFAI
1	LAD	0.46	0.68	0.74
	LCx	0.94	0.93	0.95
2	LAD	0.85	0.81	0.84
	LCx	0.73	0.69	0.75
3	LAD	0.78	0.78	0.8
	LCx	0.89	0.89	0.91
4	LAD	0.86	0.83	0.84
	LCx	0.87	0.95	0.95

Strong correlation is observed between the branch calculated vFAIs and the invasively measured FFR ($r=0.82$, $p=0.006$), as well as between the branch calculated vFAIs and the segment calculated vFAIs ($r=0.99$, $p<.0001$). Both methods (branch calculated vFAIs and segment calculated vFAIs) presented a perfect Positive Predictive Value (PPV=100%) and a Negative Predictive Value (NPV=100%), as well as a sensitivity and a specificity of 100%, since they were able to identify all cases correctly as positive to ischemia or negative, respectively. Finally, a mean difference of 0.023 (SD=0.088) is observed between the branch calculated vFAIs and the invasively measured FFR, which shows a systematic small overestimation of our method, which however, is in compliance to previous findings. Also, a small relative error of 3.2% is observed between the two methods.

IV. DISCUSSION

In this work, we presented a proof of concept study on the calculation of vFAI on coronary arterial branches, expanding its original field of application, since it had been used only on coronary arterial segments. Four patients were selected for this study, mainly due to the fact that they had FFR data for both main arteries of the left coronary branch (i.e LAD and LCx). This gave us the opportunity to calculate simultaneously the vFAI on both arteries and compare them to the invasively measured FFR, thus validating our newly proposed method. We also performed the same task but calculated the vFAI on each segment at a time (following the traditional vFAI calculation procedure). Our findings were very promising, indicating very high levels of accuracy regarding the categorization of the examined vessels to

ischemic and non-ischemic. We also observed a small trend of underestimation of the vFAI when compared to the segmental vFAI calculation, a fact that can easily be explained since a part of the Left Main artery is included in the newly proposed method. This leads to an obvious pressure drop in comparison to the segmental vFAI calculation, which however, is not quantitatively significant. Compared to the invasively measured FFR values, we observed a slight overestimation by our method, which can derive from the fact that our method strictly relies on geometrical factors and it does not take into account the microcirculatory system. Moreover, the low computational time required for each case (i.e. 20 minutes) along with its non-invasive nature and the absence of a pressure wire or the induction of hyperemia through the administration of intravenous adenosine can constitute the method highly efficient and affordable for the patient whilst improving the quality of care.

The main limitation of our study is the modest dataset that was used and needs further testing. However, we should here note that the dataset was well balanced, since it contained three pathological cases (37.5%) and five healthy ones (62.5%). We are currently expanding our dataset in order to further validate the proposed method.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The hemodynamic functional assessment of the coronary vasculature combined with its anatomic representation and visualization are of critical importance in everyday clinical practice. The results of the current study suggest that the vFAI can be effectively calculated in coronary branches and can efficiently discriminate present coronary stenoses between hemodynamically significant or non-significant.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Menke, C. Unterberg-Buchwald, W. Staab, J. M. Sohns, A. Seif Amir Hosseini, and A. Schwarz, "Head-to-head comparison of prospectively triggered vs retrospectively gated coronary computed tomography angiography: Meta-analysis of diagnostic accuracy, image quality, and radiation dose," *Am Heart J*, vol. 165, pp. 154-63 e3, Feb 2013.
- [2] M. M. Vorre and J. Abdulla, "Diagnostic accuracy and radiation dose of CT coronary angiography in atrial fibrillation: systematic review and meta-analysis," *Radiology*, vol. 267, pp. 376-86, May 2013.
- [3] B. K. Koo, A. Erglis, J. H. Doh, D. V. Daniels, S. Jegere, H. S. Kim, et al., "Diagnosis of Ischemia-Causing Coronary Stenoses by Noninvasive Fractional Flow Reserve Computed From Coronary Computed Tomographic Angiograms Results From the Prospective Multicenter DISCOVER-FLOW (Diagnosis of Ischemia-Causing Stenoses Obtained Via Noninvasive Fractional Flow Reserve) Study," *Journal of the American College of Cardiology*, vol. 58, pp. 1989-1997, Nov 1 2011.
- [4] M. Renker, U. J. Schoepf, R. Wang, F. G. Meinel, J. D. Rier, R. R. Bayer, et al., "Comparison of Diagnostic Value of a Novel Noninvasive Coronary Computed Tomography Angiography Method Versus Standard Coronary Angiography for Assessing Fractional Flow Reserve," *American Journal of Cardiology*, vol. 114, pp. 1303-1308, Nov 1 2014.
- [5] M. Kruk, L. Wardziak, M. Demkow, W. Pleban, J. Piegowski, Z. Dzielinska, et al., "Workstation-Based Calculation of CTA-Based FFR for Intermediate Stenosis," *Jacc-Cardiovascular Imaging*, vol. 9, pp. 690-699, Jun 2016.
- [6] J. K. Min, J. Leipsic, M. J. Pencina, D. S. Berman, B. K. Koo, C. van Mieghem, et al., "Diagnostic Accuracy of Fractional Flow Reserve From Anatomic CT Angiography," *Jama-Journal of the American Medical Association*, vol. 308, pp. 1237-1245, Sep 26 2012.
- [7] B. L. Norgaard, J. Leipsic, S. Gaur, S. Seneviratne, B. S. Ko, H. Ito, et al., "Diagnostic Performance of Noninvasive Fractional Flow Reserve Derived From Coronary Computed Tomography Angiography in Suspected Coronary Artery Disease The NXT Trial (Analysis of Coronary Blood Flow Using CT Angiography: Next Steps)," *Journal of the American College of Cardiology*, vol. 63, pp. 1145-1155, Apr 1 2014.
- [8] P. D. Morris, D. Ryan, A. C. Morton, R. Lycett, P. V. Lawford, D. R. Hose, et al., "Virtual fractional flow reserve from coronary angiography: modeling the significance of coronary lesions: results from the VIRTU-1 (VIRTUal Fractional Flow Reserve From Coronary Angiography) study," *JACC Cardiovasc Interv*, vol. 6, pp. 149-57, Feb 2013.
- [9] D. Tang, C. Yang, T. Geva, G. Gaudette, and P. J. Del Nido, "Multi-Physics MRI-Based Two-Layer Fluid-Structure Interaction Anisotropic Models of Human Right and Left Ventricles with Different Patch Materials: Cardiac Function Assessment and Mechanical Stress Analysis," *Comput Struct*, vol. 89, pp. 1059-1068, Jun 2011.
- [10] J. Renner, H. Nadali Najafabadi, D. Modin, T. Lanne, and M. Karlsson, "Subject-specific aortic wall shear stress estimations using semi-automatic segmentation," *Clin Physiol Funct Imaging*, vol. 32, pp. 481-91, Nov 2012.
- [11] J. Soulis, D. Fytanidis, K. Seralidou, and G. Giannoglou, "Wall shear stress oscillation and its gradient in the normal left coronary artery tree bifurcations," *Hippokratia*, vol. 18, pp. 12-6, Jan 2014.
- [12] X. Wang and X. Li, "A fluid?structure interaction study on the biomechanical behaviour of a curved artery with flexible wall," *J Med Eng Technol*, vol. 35, pp. 402-9, Nov 2011.
- [13] X. Xie, Y. Wang, H. Zhu, and J. Zhou, "Computation of hemodynamics in tortuous left coronary artery: a morphological parametric study," *J Biomech Eng*, vol. 136, p. 101006, Oct 2014.
- [14] M. I. Papafaklis, T. Muramatsu, Y. Ishibashi, L. S. Lakkas, S. Nakatani, C. V. Bourantas, et al., "Fast virtual functional assessment of intermediate coronary lesions using routine angiographic data and blood flow simulation in humans: comparison with pressure wire - fractional flow reserve," *EuroIntervention*, vol. 10, pp. 574-83, Sep 2014.
- [15] L. Athanasiou, G. Rigas, A. I. Sakellarios, T. P. Exarchos, P. K. Siogkas, C. V. Bourantas, et al., "Three-dimensional reconstruction of coronary arteries and plaque morphology using CT angiography--comparison and registration with IVUS," *BMC Med Imaging*, vol. 16, p. 9, 2016.
- [16] A. F. Frangi, W. J. Niessen, K. L. Vincken, and M. A. Viergever, "Multiscale vessel enhancement filtering," *Medical Image Computing and Computer-Assisted Intervention - Miccai'98*, vol. 1496, pp. 130-137, 1998.
- [17] C. Fuchs, T. Schwab, M. Wiczorek, M. C. Gather, S. Hofmann, K. Leo, and R. Scholz, (2014) Surface plasmon polariton modification in top-emitting organic light-emitting diodes for enhanced light outcoupling. In F. So (Ed.), *Organic Light Emitting Materials and Devices XVIII*. (Vol. 9183). (Proceedings of SPIE; Vol. 9183). SPIE-The International Society for Optical Engineering.
- [18] K. L. Gould, "Pressure-flow characteristics of coronary stenoses in unselected dogs at rest and during coronary vasodilation," *Circ Res*, vol. 43, pp. 242-53, Aug 1978.
- [19] D. F. Young, "Fluid-Mechanics of Arterial Stenoses," *Journal of Biomechanical Engineering-Transactions of the Asme*, vol. 101, pp. 157-175, 1979.
- [20] B. G. Brown, E. Bolson, M. Frimer, and H. T. Dodge, "Quantitative Coronary Arteriography - Estimation of Dimensions, Hemodynamic Resistance, and Atheroma Mass of Coronary-Artery Lesions Using Arteriogram and Digital Computation," *Circulation*, vol. 55, pp. 329-337, 1977.